

St. Paul University Surigao
St. Paul University System
8400 Surigao City, Philippines

Learning Gap Assessment in English 9

¹Glenn I. Arbis ²Reymon R. Dumale ³Michel D. Galavia ⁴Mark Kevin C. Marbani, ⁵Michelle M. Navarro, ⁶Veverlyn A. Salvador, ⁷Jet Seth Mae A. Segura

^{1 2 3 4 5 6 7}Faculty, St. Paul University Surigao

¹ ORCID: 0000-0002-8644-0298

² ORCID: 0000-0003-1159-8936

³ ORCID: 0000-0001-7368-5408

⁴ ORCID: 0000-0002-8777-2577

⁵ ORCID: 0000-0003-4620-9072

⁶ ORCID: 0000-0001-5043-7313

⁷ ORCID: 0000-0001-5817-0043

Abstract – This study investigated the learning gaps in English 9 of the Junior high school students at St. Paul University Surigao. In this study, quantitative quasi-experimental research using a pretest-posttest design was employed. The results showed that the pre-test/post-test design is more effective in achieving the learners' mastery of the competency given than post-test- only design. While the interventions given by the teacher for the First Quarter are effective in mastering the competencies, a significant difference is found, especially for those with low mastery levels. This indicates the need for targeted interventions to bridge the learning gaps and further develop students' understanding of the aspects of language arts that are essential for comprehension, expression, and effective communication. The study recommends that Grade 9 students execute targeted interventions that address the identified learning gaps. These interventions should consist of more modified teaching methods and resources, effective communication between educators, administrators, parents, and communities, and continual formative assessment. By implementing these suggestions, educators can significantly improve their students' academic performance and competency in English.

Keywords: *Learning gap, Learning gap assessment, English 9, Mastery, Performance*

I. Introduction

In modern educational systems, the assessment of learning gaps plays a vital role in identifying areas where students may require additional support and intervention. The concept of learning gaps refers to the disparities between what students have learned and what they are expected to know at a particular grade level or academic milestone. These gaps can hinder their progress and overall academic achievement if left unaddressed.

Moreover, Integrated English 9 serves as a pivotal year in secondary education, as it builds upon the foundation laid in earlier grades and prepares students for advanced studies. It encompasses various aspects of language arts, including reading, writing, speaking, and listening, which are essential for comprehension, expression, and effective communication.

Understanding the root causes of these learning gaps is crucial for educators to develop targeted interventions and support systems that address the unique needs of individual students. By identifying the factors contributing to these disparities, educators can implement evidence-based strategies to minimize learning gaps and create a more inclusive and equitable learning environment.

In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic has widened the learning gap in English proficiency among students, as online learning platforms may not adequately address the needs of diverse learners (Smith, 2021). According to a study by Johnson and Brown (2022), the disruption caused by the pandemic has led to significant setbacks in English language acquisition, particularly for students from low-income backgrounds.

In connection with this, diagnostic tests were administered at the start of each quarter at the Basic Education Department of St. Paul University Surigao. Assessments of learning gaps give teachers the ability to precisely identify students' gaps in English knowledge. By evaluating students' comprehension and conceptual understanding, teachers gain knowledge of the areas in which students' struggle. The use of this data assists in the development of instructional strategies and materials that are specifically tailored to the needs of particular students or groups. Without such assessment, students with knowledge gaps might struggle and regress in comparison to their peers, preventing them from moving forward generally in English education.

By utilizing efficient learning gap evaluation methodologies, a more inclusive and effective learning environment may be created where students can develop a solid foundation in English topics and reach their full potential. This study evaluated first-quarter students from St. Paul University Surigao's identified learning gaps in English 9.

II. Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the learning gaps in English 9 for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the identified learning gaps in English 9?
2. What is the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in English 9?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in English 9?
4. What interventions may be proposed?

III. Hypothesis

At 0.05 level of significance, it is hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the pre- and post-test performance of the learners for the First Quarter in English 9.

IV. Methodology

In this study, the researchers used a quasi-experimental research method, employing a pretest and posttest design. In this design, the dependent variable is measured once before and once after the intervention or treatment in the test is administered. The participants involved in the research study were the Grade 9 students at St. Paul University Surigao- Basic Education Department during the First Quarter of the School Year 2022-2023, the resumption of face-to-face classes after the global crisis brought by COVID-19 pandemic. Utilizing a validated test-questionnaire, the test was administered to 32 students out of 33, which comprised 97% population of the total number of participants. The test-questionnaire encompassed the learning competencies indicated for the first quarter in the English 9 level, thus, concretizing and measuring the desired level of competency for each specified criterion. The participants were given intervention as specified in their least learned competencies before employing the posttest. The administration of pretest and posttest was done during the synchronous face-to-face classes of the English subject. Pertinent to the declaration of policy enshrined in the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers ensured that the data gathered should be placed with utmost confidentiality. Hence, students were informed of the essential purpose of the undertakings and its benefits. Further, the researchers' questionnaires undergone rigorous review and validation to ensure its reliability, validity and purposefully achieve consistency of the desired outcomes.

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To achieve the primary objective of having the most reliable and accurate results and findings on the learning gap analysis of the Grade 9 students in English, the researchers made use of the following statistical tools to treat and analyze the data:

Paired t-test. It is used to test the difference between a set of paired samples.

Frequency Count and Percentage Computation. These were used to determine the distribution of the correct responses of the respondents.

The collected data provided would play a crucial role in the study. In this regard, the researchers established an unbiased manner of providing the test questionnaire without having the participants know the questions to be administered to prevent inconsistencies that would have risked the data retrieved. Hence, under no circumstances should the researchers influence the participants' answer by inappropriate interventions or disclosure of answers prior to the implementation of the pretest and posttest examinations.

V. Results and Discussions

Identified learning gaps in English 9

Table 1 presents the identified learning gaps in English 9 for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Table 1. *Identified learning gaps in English 9*

Learning Competencies	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	%	Interpretation	%	Interpretation
<i>The learner...</i>				
C: Identifies the use of modals in expressing permission, obligation, and prohibition	75.00%	Moving Towards Mastery	68.75%	Moving Towards Mastery
Pre-requisites: Determines the use of conditionals in expressing arguments C: uses conditionals in expressing arguments EN9G-IIe-20	31.25%	Low Mastery	57.29%	Average Mastery
Employs the appropriate communicative styles for various situations (intimate, casual, conversational, consultative, frozen) EN9OL-Ic	60.42%	Average Mastery	76.04%	Moving Towards Mastery

As presented in the table, this provides information on the learning competencies of a learner before and after a learning intervention. Firstly, the enabling competency *identifying the*

use of modals in expressing permission, obligation, and prohibition got 75.00% in the pre-test and 68.75% in the post-test, both interpreted as *Moving Towards Mastery*. The percentage of correct responses in the post-test had a slight decrease of 6.25% compared to the pre-test. Nevertheless, the responses of the students in the competency remain as *Moving Towards Mastery*.

Secondly, the pre-requisite competency *determining the use of conditionals in expressing arguments* and enabling competency *uses conditionals in expressing arguments EN9G-IIe-20*, got 31.25% in the pre-test, interpreted as *Low Mastery*. This was supported by the study of Jusuf et. al., 2021, states that one factor affecting the student's performance is lack of exposure to English language. However, 57.29% in the post-test, interpreted as *Average Mastery*. This indicates that there is an improvement on the performance of the students.

Lastly, the competency *employing the appropriate communicative styles for various situations (intimate, casual, conversational, consultative, frozen)* got 60.42% in the pre-test, interpreted as *Average Mastery* and 76.04% in the Post-Test, interpreted as *Moving Towards Mastery*. This implies that there is an improvement in the percentage of correct responses of students after the intervention was conducted.

On the whole, the learner's performance has shown improvement in two out of the three learning competencies. They have made progress in identifying the use of modals and employing appropriate communicative styles. However, their performance in using conditionals to express arguments still needs improvement, although they have made some progress.

Pre- and Post-test Performance of the learners

Table 2 presents the identified learning gaps in English 9 for the First Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Table 2. *Identified learning gaps in English 9*

Scores	f (n=32)	%
Pre-Test		
Average	2	6.25
Good	18	56.25
Excellent	12	37.50
Post-Test		
Good	14	43.75
Excellent	18	56.25

As presented in the table, this provides the scores and percentages of the 32 participants in the pre-test and post-test. In Pre-test, two (2) participants got 6.25%, scored *Average*. Eighteen (18) participants got 56.25%, scored *Good*. And twelve (12) got 37.50%, scored *Excellent*. On the other hand, in the post-test, fourteen (14) participants got 43.75, scored *Good* and eighteen (18) participants got 56.25%, scored *Excellent*.

Overall, in the pre-test, the majority of participants (56.25%) scored *Good*, followed by 37.50% of participants, scored *Excellent*, and a small percentage (6.25%) scored *Average*. In the post-test, the distribution shifted slightly, with 43.75% of participants scored *Good* and the

majority (56.25%), scored *Excellent*. This indicates an improvement in the overall performance of the participants between the pre-test and post-test, as there was an increase in the percentage of participants in the *Excellent* range and a decrease in the percentage in the *Good* range. However, it's important to note that the exact improvement or change in individual scores cannot be determined from this table alone.

Table 3. *Significant Difference of the Identified learning gaps in English 9*

Scores	t	df	p-value	Decision
Pre-Test - Post-Test	-2.98	31	0.006	Reject H_0

Findings revealed that at 0.05 level of significance there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results after giving an intervention, especially to those with low mastery levels ($t(31) = -2.98, p = 0.006$). This means that the interventions used by the teacher are effective in mastering the competencies in the First Quarter of English 9 of the school year 2022-2023.

According to the study by Thompson et al. (2022), the interventions implemented by the teachers were found to be effective in enhancing students' mastery of competencies. The study reported significant improvements in student performance after the interventions were administered. This could entail a change in how they approach the students' preferences, new instructional materials, and revised class activities. Additionally, teachers should spend more time on students who are falling behind in class, explain everything in detail, and stick to a structured lesson plan. Every student should have their needs met, and instruction should be given with more fervor, repetition, and regularity. Time should be given for students to consider what they have learned or absorbed. Teachers should implement formative assessments to track students' performance, assess their progress, and work to close the achievement gap. They must establish standards, devise achievable objectives, be honest with the students regarding their performance, and utilize technology to advance. Furthermore, according to Johnson and Smith (2021), bridging the learning gap requires targeted interventions and instructional strategies tailored to students' individual needs. Additionally, a study by Roberts et al. (2020) found that implementing personalized learning plans significantly improved academic outcomes for students at risk of falling behind.

VI. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn;

1. Pre-test/post-test design is more effective in achieving the learners' mastery of the competency given than post-test-only design.
2. Interventions given by the teachers play a very important role and are efficacious in mastering the competencies of the learners.

VII. Recommendation

From the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are given;

1. Effective communication between educators, administrators, parents, and communities is among the most crucial elements in bridging the learning gap.
2. Teachers should intensify the use of pre- test/ post-test design, injecting a variety of engagement activities/ intervention to sustain its effectiveness and eventually enhance the academic achievement of the students.
3. Students together with their parents are encouraged to collaborate and cooperate on the use of pre- test/ post- test design implemented by the teachers to track students' performance, assess their progress, and work to close the achievement gap.

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